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Changing Pattern of Agricultural Productivity in North East India : A Regional Interpretation

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Abstract : Present paper examines the pattern of changing pattern of agricultural productivity and agricultural production systems prevalent in the North-East Region. Calculating agricultural productivity in its money term for two points of time - 1998-99 (liberalisation period) and 2008-09 (post-liberalisation), it is found that the agricultural productivity is changing very fast all over the North-east region of the country. Especially, hill areas have experienced very high increase in agricultural productivity. It happened due to two main reasons: first, a fast change in the food grain dominated cropping pattern to commercial cropping because farmers wish to grow high value crops to maximise their profit and, secondly, the growing market economy and expanding road network in rural areas which have been helping in regulating agricultural products within and outside North-East Region.

Keywords : Agricultural Productivity Pattern, General Productivity Pattern, Processes of change.

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Introduction

In general agricultural productivity change conceals considerable regional differences because of farming practices, techniques availability of irrigation facilities, attitude of the farmers and so on. The difference of agricultural productivity change among the regions to some extent is a natural phenomenon, such as rainfall, temperature, humidity and some other agro-ecological factors influence productivity. It is not only the natural phenomenon but also population increase and government policies relating to agricultural extension, input distribution, institutional credit facilities, agricultural co-operatives, and some basic/institutional inefficiency are the causes of productivity variations in the regions. The era of mechanized agriculture began with the invention of such agricultural machines like reaper, cultivator, thresher, combine harvester and tractors, which continued to appear

over the years leading to a new type of large scale agriculture (Altson et al. 2010). Industrial revolution also changes the behavior of the farmers in selection of agricultural crops with the need of agro-based industry.

In North-East Region of the country the agricultural type and pattern are diverse, ranging from subsistence to commercial types. It appears that the result of variability in resource endowments, physiography, climate, institution, technology and socio-economic factors. As a consequence, production performance of agricultural sector has followed uneven path and the large variations have been seen in productivity between agro-ecological zones or among districts. Large variations in productivity lead to regional disparity. Identification of various level of productivity helps to analyze the reason behind such variations that may control the future growth and development patterns. Such variations

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in productivity also indicate scope to raise production and productivity attaining balanced agricultural growth. In the present work attention is focused to describe the regional pattern of agricultural productivity and changes therein to visualize the changing pattern of productivity in general in order to study its factors. Classificatory approach is adopted to describe the productivity pattern.

Methodology

In the present case, agricultural productivity refers to land productivity that is defined as total agricultural output per unit of cultivated area. Going through the literature available on measurement of agricultural output, it is widely accepted that agricultural production is the result of combinations of infra-structural elements, viz, physical, techno-economic, socio-cultural, etc. by which agricultural efficiency is influenced (Singh and Chauhan, 1977). Since market price of agricultural product is influencing factor of agricultural output, the economists considered three elements of agriculture (Area, Yield and Price of crops) to measure the total output in terms of money value. For the purpose of aggregated agricultural output, the following standard formula used by Bhalla and Tyagi (1989) and Singh (1994), has been adopted:

$$O = \sum (A_i \cdot Y_i \cdot P_i) \tag{1}$$

Then agricultural productivity is simply the output per unit of cultivated land as

$$Y = (O/A) \tag{2}$$

Change in agricultural productivity over time

$$C = (t_0) - t_1 \tag{3}$$

where, Y = agricultural productivity per areal unit, A_i = area of ith Crop, Y_i = yield of ith Crop, P_i = harvest price of ith Crop, O = total agricultural output in its money term, C= change over time, (t₀) = base year, (t₁) = current year.

For the purpose of analyzing changing pattern of agricultural productivity, the conversion of area and yield of the various crops has been used for two points of time (i.e. 1998-99 and 2008-09). Thus, the agricultural output of each of the areal unit (District) has been calculated by converting crop production in to its money term with the help of multiplying the total production of each crop by its constant harvest price of the base year (1998-99).

The regional analysis of agricultural productivity is solely based on secondary data collected district wise from Ministry of Information and Technology, Government of India and other government publications. Farm harvest price of 1998-99 is considered for both the time periods, 1998-99 the liberalisation phase and 2008-09 the Post-liberalisation phase of economic growth. A total number of 32 crops were included for the calculation of the total agricultural output. Classifying districts in to five productivity classes, the general pattern are visualized and studied. They are there are the areas of: (i) Very High Productivity (Above Rs 20,000/ha), (ii) High (Rs 15,000/ha - Rs 20,000/ha), (iii) Medium (Rs 10,000/ha - Rs 15,000/ha), (iv) Low (Rs 5,000/ha - Rs 10,000/ha) and (v) Very Low Productivity (Below Rs 5,000/ha).

Class Wise Interpretation of Agriculture Productivity

The general interpretation of inter-district variations in agricultural productivity envisaged the differences and inequality of development of agricultural productivity level within the study areas. Such variation over times provides the general understanding the speed and influx of agricultural technology and transformation.

1) Very High Productivity (Above Rs 20,000/ha)

During the liberalization period, the Areas of Very High agriculture productivity are confined only in 7 districts including Manipur Valley, Parts of Nagaland and N.C. Hills and Tripura (Fig-1A). While the occupied areas of was remarkably increased from 8.43% of total crop areas to more than 21.56% of the total crop areas (24 districts) during the period of post-liberalization (1998-99 to 2008-09). These mean that the surrounding areas of Patkai Hills and Eastern Himalaya and the entire Meghalaya Plateau including Karbi Hills of Assam were included in the expansion areas of Very High Productivity (Fig - 1B). During the decade, very high productivity class experienced significant declining trends of food grain crops area up to 21.43 % (Table - 1).

2) High (Rs 15,000/ha - Rs 20,000/ha)

High agricultural productivity areas is identified in 10 districts and occupying around 15.94% of the total cropped areas, which are generally confined in the Manipur valley and Southern parts of Nagaland in 1998-99 (Fig-1A). However, in 2008-09 the high agricultural productivity areas are noticed in hills

and plain areas. It account 23 districts and 41.8% of the cropped areas are falling under this category (Fig-1B). Similar to the above class, food grain crops area is decline 6.46% from 88.68% to 82.22% in between 1998-99 to 2008-09 respectively.

3) Medium (Rs 10,000/ha - Rs 15,000/ha):

In 998-99, most of the areas of Eastern and Southern Hills Central Hills and Valley, Meghalaya Plateau and some plain areas of Tripura Hills and Valleys are included in this category. The percentage contribution of food grain crops area is significantly high and 93.67% of the crop area was under food grain crops. Contrary to base year, in 2008-09 numbers of districts falling under medium productivity areas are increased and identified in 18 districts of Tripura, Mizoram, Arunachal Pradesh and Lower and Upper Assam Valley. And counting 35.18% of total crops areas are falling under this category. While, the percentage shares of food grain crops was shrinking 10.67%. It means that the percentage share of commercial crops was increased up to 10.67% during the ten years (Table - 1 & 2).

4) Low (Rs 5,000/ha - Rs 10,000/ha):

During the base year, low productivity category are recognized in 24 districts, isolated districts of Purvanchal North, Meghalaya Plateau, Mizoram and alluvial soil district of Lower and Central Brahmaputra Valley. Food grain crops were occupied 39.41% of the total crop areas of the North-Eastern Region. But, only 5 districts are falling under low agricultural productivity in 2008-09. Generally, food grain crops are dominant crop in low

agricultural productivity. Though, in this class the percentage share of food grains areas was increased 7.56% during the ten years.

5) Very Low Productivity (Below Rs 5,000/ha):

During the ten years, more than 10% of the total crops area were occupied by very low productivity and counting 21 districts in 1998-99 (Fig-1A). At 2008-09 the numbers of district falling under very low productivity are found in two southern districts of Mizoram. Similarly, during ten years the percentage share of food grains was increased up to 23.96% in this category (Table - 1).

Productivity class wise comparison of the productivity distribution would show its transformation processes cropping pattern and crop diversification.

The comparison of area and output shares provide basis of productivity changes. These changes are discussed in the in the following.

A. Changes in Productivity Pattern

Comparing two map of agricultural productivity (Figs. - 1A & 1B), it is clear that the obliterated high and very high productivity pattern of 1998-99 has become unified by adding more areas under these categories of high and very high productivity. Expansion of this category was mostly in the hill and mountain areas of Arunachal Himalaya, Patkai Hills and Lushai Hills of the South. Most of the Meghalaya Plateau also raised productivity level from medium (1998-99) to very high (2008-09). Changing ratio of area and output of crops show the characteristic features of production transformation.

Fig-1: Levels of Agricultural Productivity in (A) 1998-99 and (B) 2008-09 Changing Pattern of Agricultural Productivity (1998-99 to 2008-09):

(B) Changes in Area and Output of Food Grain Crops

There is a decrease in the food grain crop area in moderate and very high productivity classes which shows that the cropping pattern is gradually transformed from food grain dominated to commercial crops. Food grains are low value crops so the production of food grains also decreases in this class of high productivity. Table - 1 reveals that there has been fairly high decrease of 25.50% percent from 78.72% to 53.22% in the food grain output with in the decade. In terms of areas and output, the percentage share of food grains has been declined towards high to low productivity classes (Table - 1) Such negative changes in food grain area and output shows that the cropping pattern changes fast in the North-East Region of the country. It affects productivity.

(C) Changes in Area and Output of Commercial Crops

In the North-East India, commercial crops became important to grow fast during the late 1990's when liberalization policies were adopted in

the other part of the country. It may be due to its remote location, cultural diversity, technological lag, knowledge know how of farmer and poor economic setup. In between 1998-99 to 2008-09, the commercial crops became more popular. These crops occupy area of about 14.67 % to the total cropped area in North-East Region in 1998-99 that has been expanded to 16.08 % in 2008-09 (i.e. 1.41%) during the period of ten years. On the other hand, the total output of these crops was increased 25.48 % from 21.29 % to 46.77 % during the same period of time (Table - 2). Comparing the changes in area and output of commercial crops, it is fact the area under these crop were raised marginally but production contribution became about a half of the total agricultural production as it was raised from 4.9 million tons (1998-99) to 45.4 million tons (2008-09). It means the main thrust of adoption of technology (use of fertilizer, pesticides and HYVs of seeds) was towards the production and productivity increased of commercial crops.

The evidence of the same fact can

Table - 1: Change in Area and output of Food Grains Crops in Different Productivity Classes in 1998-99 to 2008-09

Sl.No	Productivity Class	Food Grain Area (ha)			Food Grain Output (Rs Lakh)		
		1998-99 (%)	2008-09 (%)	Change (%)	1998-99 (%)	2008-09 (%)	Change (%)
1	Very High (Above Rs 20000)	94.75	73.32	-21.43	62.31	22.00	-40.31
2	High (Rs 15000-20000)	88.68	82.22	-6.46	74.94	53.04	-21.90
3	Medium (Rs 10000-15000)	93.67	83.00	-10.67	81.24	54.19	-27.05
4	Low (Rs 5000-10000)	85.55	93.11	7.56	89.33	73.12	-16.21
5	Very Low (Below Rs 5000)	63.98	87.94	23.96	85.78	63.78	-22.00
6	Average	85.33	83.91	-1.42	78.72	53.22	-25.50

Source: Compiled by Researcher

be seen by establishing relationship between changes in area and output of commercial crops with productivity level. The areas of Low productivity level have lesser changes in area and output of commercial crops rather than the areas of the High productivity level are accompanied by high changes of area in North-East Region (Figs. - 4.5 & 4.6).

There has been increase of commercial output in each of the productivity classes (Table - 2). The percentage share of area under commercial crops increased about 21.43 percent and its output about 40.31% during the last ten years in the area of Very high productivity (Rs 20000 and above per hectare). These ratios of area and output of commercial crops are shrinking down in low productivity areas. It shows that cropping pattern changes fast from food grains to commercial crops especially in high productivity areas.

Findings and Conclusion

The farmers were concentrated to grow agricultural crops only for their

subsistence level prior to implementation of economic policies. But, the pattern of agricultural land use and productivity have been becoming more market oriented and production of high value when they realized the importance of market and strong road network which was expanded during the early part of 20th century. There has been fast change in cropping and productivity pattern during the post-liberalization phase of economic development in the North-East Region. Such interesting changing pattern of agricultural productivity have peculiar characteristic as:

- (a) The areas having medium and low productivity level in 1998-99 have fast change in productivity during the decade considered for. In 2008-09, about 63.37% of the total crop areas (47 out of 72 districts) are under the areas having high and very high productivity level. This means that agricultural productivity is increased in the moderate productivity areas. The main driving factors of productivity increased in

Table – 2: Change in Area and output of Commercial Crops in Different Productivity Classes in 1998-99 to 2008-09

Sl.No	Productivity Class	Commercial Crop Area (ha)			Commercial Crop Output (Rs Lakh)		
		1998-99 (%)	2008-09 (%)	Change (%)	1998-99 (%)	2008-09 (%)	Change (%)
1	Very High (Above Rs 20000)	5.25	26.68	21.43	37.69	78.00	40.31
2	High (Rs 15000-20000)	11.32	17.78	6.46	25.06	46.96	21.90
3	Medium (Rs 10000-15000)	6.33	17.00	10.67	18.76	45.81	27.05
4	Low (Rs 5000-10000)	14.45	6.89	-7.56	10.67	26.88	16.21
5	Very Low (Below Rs 5000)	36.01	12.05	-23.96	14.26	36.21	21.95
6	Average	14.67	16.08	1.41	21.29	46.77	25.48

Source: Compiled by Researcher

the North-East Region are due to the changes of cropping pattern and improvement of agricultural technology (irrigation, HYV seeds and road etc.) in North-East Region of the country.

- b) Increasing area under food grain crops do not have effect on productivity level and its increase (Fig - 2A). Rate of increase in productivity is much faster than the

increased in the area of food grain crops (Fig. - 2B). It means that increasing area under food grain crops does not have much effect on productivity. However the percentage share of food grain areas and output has been increased particularly in plain areas due to introduction of irrigation technology in the area and increasing demand of food grains, so the productivity

Fig. - 2: (A) Change of Food Grain Crops Productivity in 1998-99 and (B) Changes in Productivity of Food Grain Crops in 1998-99 to 2008-09

Fig. - 3: (A) Change in Commercial Crops Area in 1998-99 to 2008-09 and (B) Change in Commercial Crops Output in 1998-99 to 2008-09

level is observed low in these areas.

- c) The occupied area of commercial crops became more in the North-East Region. The occupied area of commercial crops is unequal in all over the North-East Region in the beginning of liberalization and after ten years it becomes more uniform. Along with the increased of areas the output contribution of commercial crops to total output is increased during the ten years.
- d) The occupied area of commercial crops is unequal in all over the North-East Region in the beginning of liberalization and after ten years it becomes more uniform. Along with the increased of areas the output contribution of commercial crops to total output is increased during the ten years. In the areas of low productivity the percentage share of area under commercial crops has been reduce. Inversely, the area under commercial crops increased fast up to even 21.43% in very high productivity areas of hills and mountains.
- e) Only a few patches of high productivity (in the hill areas) have been expanded up to the half of the North-East area during the ten years. It happened due to changing pattern from food grain dominated (1998-99) to horticulture and fruits crop dominated (2008-09). Hill areas have potentials to expand horticultural crops because of humid climate, fertile soils and bio-diversity in this area.

References

- Alston, J. M., Bruce A., Babcock and Philip G. Pardey (2010) : *The Shifting Patterns of Agricultural Productivity in World Wide*, The Midwest Agribusiness Trade Research and Information Center, Iowa State University, USA
- Bhalla, G. S. and D. S. Tyagi (1989) : *Pattern in Indian Agricultural Development- A District Level Study*, Institute for Studies in Industrial Development, New Delhi
- Binswanger, H. P (1978) : *Introduced Technological Change-Evaluation of Thought*, Johns Hopkins University Press
- Boserup, E. (1965) : *The Conditions of Agricultural Growth*, George Allen and Unwin, London
- Singh, S. (1994) : *Agricultural Development in India: A Regional Analysis*, Kaushal Prakashan, Shillong
- Singh, S. and V. S. Chauhan (1977) : *Measurement of Agricultural Productivity- A Case Study of Utter Pradesh*, *Indian Geographical Review of India*, 39: 222-31